

Definition of Requirements and System Engineering of the Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket (BANTER)

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Abstract

BANTER (Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket) is a four-year project funded by the European Innovation Council which aims to demonstrate the operating principles of a complete bimodal nuclear propulsion system where ammonia is used either as propellant for nuclear thermal and electric propulsion and as working fluid for the electric power generation cycle. The implementation of both nuclear thermal and electric propulsion allows for a significant increase in the spectrum of maneuvers that can be performed while maintaining a reduced size and mass, thanks to the sharing of the most critical components, such as the reactor and the propellant management system. Bimodal propulsion systems can perform hybrid maneuvers, combining the advantages of both low-energy and low-thrust transfer methods, which allow for a reduction in propellant consumption compared to the use of only one of the two propulsion technologies. This work describes the system engineering applied to BANTER, which is fundamental to achieving the project goals due to the coexistence of many subsystems strongly connected by the most critical components in a compact and versatile configuration. A preliminary design of the nuclear thermal and electric propulsion systems, based on a parametric analysis of the nuclear reactor, serves as a basis for the mission analysis of the bimodal nuclear rocket. The mission analysis aims to identify the optimal sequence of maneuvers to complete missions of interest for the main space agencies in the next decades. The ultimate goal of the mission analysis is to obtain a list of requirements necessary for the detailed design of BANTER during the subsequent project phases. Particular attention is given to the safety requirements of the mission to be carried out: prevention of nuclear reactor unplanned criticality, definition of the nuclear safe orbit, payload protection from radiation, safe final reactor disposal, avoidance of inadvertent atmosphere reentry and radioactive material scattering, and ability to keep the reactor subcritical in case of ocean water immersion are just a few examples of the safety features that will be required to BANTER. The system analysis and the imposed requirements will highlight the capabilities of the various operational modes of BANTER, showing how a fully bimodal propulsion system can become a game-changer technology for future space mission scenarios.

Keywords: System Engineering; Ammonia; Bimodal; NTP; NEP; In-Situ Resource Utilization

Nomenclature

A = cross section area
 A_v = fuel particle surface area
 C_h = Stanton number
 C_i' = modified concentration of i -th delayed neutron precursor
 c_p = specific heat
 D_p = particle diameter
 h = convective heat transfer coefficient
 k = thermal conductivity
 k_{eff} = criticality constant
 L = length
 m = mass
 \dot{m} = mass flow rate
 N_p = pump rotational speed
 n_s = pump specific velocity
 P = power
 p = pressure

R_{cv} = control volume equivalent flow resistance
 Q = heat exchanged
 q'' = power per surface unit
 r = radius
 T = temperature
 t_b = burn time
 U = convection coefficient
 u = speed
 δ = power density
 ε = porosity
 η = efficiency
 ξ = reactivity change
 ρ = density

Subscripts

c = thrust chamber
channel = reactor's coolant channel
e = electric motor
f = fuel
i = inverter (before Eq.9)
i = i-th element or layer (after Eq.8)
in = pump inlet
out = pump outlet
p = propellant
part = fuel particle
pump = pump properties

Acronyms/Abbreviations

BANTER = Bimodal Ammonia Nuclear Thermal and Electric Rocket
EPS = Electric Propulsion System
IMLEO = Initial Mass in LEO
IMNSO = Initial Mass in NSO
LLO = Low Lunar Orbit
MPD = Magnetoplasmadynamics
NEP = Nuclear Electric Propulsion
NPPS = Nuclear Power and Propulsion System
NRHO = Near Rectilinear Halo Orbit
NSO = Nuclear Safe Orbit
NTP = Nuclear Thermal Propulsion
PGS = Power Generation System
PMS = Propellant Management System
RCS = Attitude Control System
TLI = Trans-Lunar Injection

1. Introduction

BANTER is a European Innovation Council project involving the development of technologies necessary to raise up to TRL 4 of a bimodal nuclear propulsion system for space application using ammonia as the propellant. As highlighted in a companion paper [1], the innovation introduced with BANTER is the possibility to make the entire system dependent on a single fluid; the ammonia is not only the propellant for the NTP and the NEP, but also the coolant for the reactor structure (allowing the recuperation of thermal energy), the working fluid for a Brayton thermodynamic cycle generating the electric power and the pressurant for the propellant management system thanks to an autogenous pressurizing configuration [2]. The use of a single fluid within the entire system makes the various subsystems highly interconnected, a connection made even stronger by the presence of the nuclear reactor. This

element is central to the BANTER system because, based on bimodality, it is used both to generate high thrust for the NTP and to generate electrical power for the various system components. The initial layout of the reactor includes, as shown in Fig. 1, a single moderator block containing 37 channels (arranged in 4 rings with a hexagonal lattice) filled with fuel in the form of small particles (as in a Particle Bed Reactor) and surrounded by a reflector with 16 rotating drums for reactivity control. The channels were designed to allow a complete ammonia decomposition at their outlet, which represents of the main innovations introduced by BANTER to raise the NTP specific impulse up to 500 s [3]. Further details on the preliminary design of the reactor can be found in [4]. The first phase of the project concerns the identification of mission scenarios of interest to space agencies in the coming decades, on which to base a list of requirements necessary for the design of the entire BANTER system. In this sense, having a preliminary reactor design helped in choosing the most appropriate mission scenarios because it provided a rough estimate of the size and performance of the system's central component. The preliminary design and some key requirements allowed for several mission analyses to be performed. From these analyses, additional constraints were defined to drive the next phases of the project, focused on the design, development, and testing of the key technologies involved within the BANTER system. This paper describes the rationale behind the conducted mission analyses and the main constraints obtained as outputs. It also demonstrates the methodology that will be applied in the subsequent project steps to achieve the initial design of the most critical elements, such as the nuclear reactor and the electrical power generation system. These elements are closely interconnected and form the basis for the proper functioning of every other subsystem of the proposed configuration. Moreover, they include significant innovations compared to what has been proposed to date in the literature on nuclear propulsion systems in space, as it will be described below. Finally, a discussion of the safety aspects that led to the formulation of some key requirements in this area is presented. It is worth noting that, to date, there are no global safety regulations for the development of such propulsion systems as stringent as those for the development of terrestrial nuclear systems, making it difficult to determine requirements to follow for achieving a design that is globally accepted as safe. Nevertheless, the international use of nuclear power in space is governed by a range of treaties and principles that aim to promote peaceful cooperation, safety, and respect for the celestial environment. The UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS) operates on the principle of consensus, requiring that all reports be adopted without formal disagreement. Key guidelines of this committee are:

- “Principles Relevant to the Use of Nuclear Power Sources in Outer Space” developed in 1993 and emphasizing the importance of safety, risk assessment, and minimizing contamination of space and celestial bodies [5] ;
- “Safety Framework for Nuclear Power Source Applications in Outer Space” developed in 2009 and providing a high-level guidance in the form of a model safety framework. It is voluntary and non-binding, however states such as Russia, China and the US have publicly declared to follow the Safety Framework [6].

The Working Group on the Use of Nuclear Power Sources in Outer Space, being part of the United Nations Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA) has a long record of productive work and has developed the Safety Framework jointly with the International Atomic Energy Agency. Currently the Working Group is working under a 5-year workplan (2024 – 2028) with 3 main objectives [7]:

- Promote and facilitate the implementation of the Safety Framework for nuclear power source applications in outer space;
- Collect and analyze relevant technical information about potential future uses of nuclear power sources in outer space;
- Discuss within the Working Group the implications of the in objective 2 described analysis.

All the above documents represent a good base to start identifying the safety aspects that should drive the BANTER project.

Fig. 1: BANTER's Reactor Initial Layout

2. The BANTER System

BANTER is composed of five systems, as shown in Fig. 2: the Nuclear Propulsion System (NPS), the Power Generation System (PGS), the Attitude Control System (RCS), the Propellant Management System (PMS), and the Electric Propulsion System (EPS). The various systems are connected to each other via mechanical, fluidic, and electrical interfaces. Thanks to the above systems, BANTER can exploit two different propulsion modes that can operate independently: the NTP mode for high thrust and the electric propulsion mode for high efficiency.

Fig. 2: BANTER System and Subsystems Schematic

The NTP system consists of ammonia propellant, which is pressurized from the main tank to high pressures (preliminary design, between 70 and 100 bar) by two E-pumps before entering the nuclear reactor. Inside the reactor channels, it absorbs large amounts of thermal energy, which then converts into kinetic energy through expansion in the nozzles integrated into the reactor ducts, before exiting at high speeds to generate the required thrust.

The PGS consists of ammonia working fluid, which is pressurized from the main tank to high pressures (preliminary design, around 100 bar) by an E-pump before entering dedicated heating channels located within the nuclear reactor

core. Inside the channels, the ammonia reaches the temperature required by the imposed thermodynamic cycle and exits, entering and expanding in the turbine. Connected to the turbine shaft, a generator transforms the work done by the ammonia during expansion into electrical energy, made available by the power conditioning to the various system components and/or on-board users. Finally, the low-pressure ammonia, after exiting the turbine, enters a second tank (pressurizing tank); inside this tank, the excess energy assimilated by the ammonia flowing into the nuclear reactor must be dissipated and different strategies are implemented: 1) an E-pump sends liquid ammonia from the main tank to the pressurizing tank where it will absorb part of the energy of the ammonia vapor causing a partial phase change, 2) the ammonia vapor is sent to the electric thrusters and warm gas thrusters to power them and at the same time reduce the pressure in the tank, 3) the ammonia is sent, via an E-pump, back into the reactor to perform an expander cycle and exit at high temperatures from the NTP system, 4) use the ammonia as a pressurizer for the main tank (autogenous pressurization). All four implementable strategies make the PGS characterized by an open Brayton cycle (the ammonia exits the system) and asynchronous (the ammonia exits the system with a certain delay with respect to the moment of exit from the turbine).

The RCS is composed of multiple thrusters that expel ammonia vapor from the system to generate the momentum required for the system's attitude change; the thrusters' firing reduces the overpressure generated by the PGS operation inside the pressurizing tank.

The PM system is connected to all other BANTER subsystems and as described previously, sends propellant to the reactor, the power generation system, the warm gas thrusters, and the electric thrusters via E-pumps. Furthermore, the presence of various tanks enables autogenous pressurization, a key feature of the BANTER system, which makes it dependent on a single fluid. This feature can also be used to base an ISRU strategy [4,8].

Magnetoplasmadynamic (MPD) thrusters are high-power electromagnetic propulsion devices that utilize electromagnetic forces to accelerate the propellant. An MPD thruster consists of a central cathode (which can be a rod or a hollow cathode) surrounded by a cylindrical or nozzle-formed anode and insulated with proper insulators. Amongst steady state MPD thrusters there are two types: self-field MPD thrusters, where an azimuthal magnetic field is generated only by the internal plasma current flowing from cathode to anode; applied-field MPD thrusters, where an external magnetic field, often in the form of a solenoid, is used to provide an additional magnetic field that can help stabilize discharge instabilities and produce additional acceleration of the plasma. Applied-field magnetoplasmadynamic thrusters (AF-MPDT) have been actively researched in the past decades, and are currently promising technologies for high power space missions. They have input powers of up to several 100 kW and reach very high thrust densities with respect to other electric propulsion devices, and high specific impulses (Isp), which enables their usage in interplanetary space missions and for space tugs for example to the Moon or Mars [9]. Recent thruster developments use high temperature superconductor (HTS) coils, to generate the applied field, which is an important step to move the thruster technology closer to its utilization in space flight [10].

3. System Analysis and Key Requirements

The first step in the BANTER system analysis process was the formulation of a preliminary mission analysis. Given the high versatility in the type of maneuvers achievable by the system, the focus on three main propulsive options determines the constraints each propulsion mode would introduce. The first option involved the study of a mission conducted only in NTP mode, and therefore only with the use of high-thrust impulsive maneuvers; the second option evaluated mission scenarios accomplishable using only the NEP, and therefore with low-thrust maneuvers and long durations; finally, the third option investigated missions employing hybrid maneuvers performed with NTP and NEP. The mission scenarios were chosen arbitrarily and, based on the outcome of future designs of the various subsystems, may be subject to modifications. However, some requirements used to set the mission analyses and future designs, called key requirements, will constitute non-modifiable constraints around which the BANTER system must be designed. Table 1 lists the key requirements. Sec. 8 presents the rationale for the determination of the safety requirements.

Table 1: BANTER Key Requirements

Key Requirements
The system shall prevent unplanned nuclear reactor criticality during launch and mission
The system shall maintain the nuclear reactor's core integrity (except possibly on planned dispersal on atmospheric re-entry)
The system shall provide radiological safety in case of random impact location from a launch abort
The system shall allow a safe reactor final disposal
The system shall prevent reentry into the biosphere after operation
The system shall protect the crew/payload against unacceptable radiation levels
The system shall be safe, independent, and high reliable
The system shall assure that in case of certain number of failures the mission can be completed, and the crew/payload is protected.
The system shall emit radiation levels sufficiently low prior to launch to avoid special handling precautions
The likelihood of an inadvertent reentry shall be $< 10^{-4}$ over the mission life
The combined probability of inadvertent reentry plus scattering shall be $< 10^{-6}$;
In the case of intact reentry, the scattering of radioactive components shall be confined to an impact zone with a radius of less than 1 km.
The overall propulsion system mass shall be compliant with the selected launcher constraint for insertion in the selected initial Nuclear Safe Orbit
The overall propulsion system envelope shall be compliant with the selected launcher constraint for insertion in the selected initial Nuclear Safe Orbit
The propulsion system shall use ammonia as propellant and working fluid
The propulsion system shall be able to be refilled with ammonia in-orbit
The propulsion system shall be able to remove the nuclear reactor's decay and waste heat to avoid increases in the components temperatures over the allowed limits
The propulsion system shall be able to perform high-thrust maneuvers
The propulsion system shall be able to perform low-thrust maneuvers
The propulsion system shall be able to perform hybrid maneuvers
The propulsion system shall be able to perform attitude control maneuvers
The operations of each subsystem shall be guaranteed in some extent even in the case of failures of other subsystems
All system operations shall be capable of being performed autonomously under the overall control of the spacecraft

4. NEP-mode Mission Outputs

The mission scenario using only NEP, described in a companion paper [11], provides an estimate of the maximum expected transit times for the propulsion system, which are essential for imposing requirements on the maximum continuous operation time of the power generation system, i.e., the required energy. The scenarios analyzed for the NEP-only solution involved a cargo mission to the Moon (both single-trip and round-trip) and a cargo mission to Mars (both single-trip and round-trip). This was done to try to size the system for missions likely to be of interest to most space agencies, following the objectives of the coming decades.

The input parameters used for the NEP scenarios towards the Moon and Mars are reported in Table 2.

Table 2: NEP Mission Input Parameters

Parameter	Value
IMLEO (t)	30
BANTER engine dry mass (t)	4
Power available for electric thrusters	200 kWe
NSO altitude (km)	900
Lunar Orbit altitude (km)	100
Mars Orbit altitude (km)	250

The details of the analysis are described in a companion paper [11]. Below is a summary of the results of interest for the requirements formulation, following both the NEP-Moon and NEP-Mars scenarios. Considering a thruster power requirement of approximately 200 kW, the round-trip mission to the Moon requires a thruster operational period of 350 days for an optimized payload fraction of approximately 0.45 with a thrust of 7.4 N and a specific impulse of 4447 s. Maintaining the same time limit for electric thruster operation for the mission to Mars, with similar thrust and specific impulse values and equal power, the payload fraction is reduced to approximately 0.25.

Considering the results of this limit-case analysis, in which BANTER operates only in NEP mode, it is possible to determine the maximum operational period and maximum power required by the NEP system, which will produce a maximum constraint on the power generation system. Table 3 reports these constraints.

Table 3: NEP Mission Output Constraints

Constraint	Value
Maximum MPD Required Power (kWe)	200
Maximum MPD Required Operating Period (d)	350

5. NTP-mode Mission Outputs

The other limiting case sees the BANTER system operating only in NTP mode. The mission scenario considered for this case involved a multiple round-trip mission to the Moon with the possibility of ammonia refilling in the Low Lunar Orbit; the mission details are reported in [4]. The analysis assumes that the ammonia did not dissociate inside the nuclear reactor, and, therefore, a very conservative value for the specific impulse was chosen. The strategy is in line with the objectives of the study, which aims to provide a conservative estimate of the maximum quantity of ammonia propellant (and not working fluid) used by the system on a mission to the Moon. Using the preliminary layout for the NTP system, characterized by the values reported in Table 4, a required propellant mass, at the beginning of the mission in Earth orbit, of approximately 20.5 t and a pressurizing tank volume of about 4.5 m³ were estimated; these values represent another limiting constraint for the BANTER system.

Table 4: NTP Mission Input Parameters

Parameter	Value
TLI (m/s)	3288
Moon circularization (LLO) (m/s)	900
LLO-NRHO roundtrip (m/s)	1404
IMNSO (t)	30
Specific Impulse (s)	370

6. Hybrid-mode Mission Outputs

Finally, the last case study concerns the analysis of a mission scenario using bimodality, i.e., hybrid maneuvers with segments performed by NEP and segments performed by NTP. The analyzed case involved a mission starting from NSO, arriving in lunar orbit for propellant refilling, and then a one-way trip to Mars. For this case, for which more information can be found in [12], the constraints imposed by the previous cases were adopted, i.e., a maximum operating time for each segment lower than the threshold given by the “only-NEP” mode (< 350 days) and a maximum propellant mass of approximately 20.5 t for each segment. With these constraints, an initial mass of approximately 50 t (considering also the payload mass) can be associated with the bimodal system, and the optimization results for the hybrid maneuvers performed in the two segments (first segment – Earth-Moon, second segment Moon-Mars) are reported in Table 5. From the table, it is possible to verify that the constraint on propellant mass was respected, as well as that on transport times: this demonstrates, as already highlighted in some works in the literature, that hybrid maneuvers allow for shorter transit times than those of systems using only the NEP, but with greater efficiencies in terms of propellant consumption than those of systems using only the NTP. The payload fraction for this system was calculated for two different values of the propulsion system mass: a worst-case scenario with a propulsion system dry mass of approximately 13 t and a best-case scenario with a dry mass of about 8 t. It is worth to underline that these masses are greater than those used in the two previous cases and this is due to the increase in IMNSO which caused a scaling of the mass of the propulsion system (for example, to maintain the impulsive

maneuver hypothesis, the thrust was increased with a consequent increase in the size of the reactor and its mass). The difference between the two scenarios lies in the possible optimization that can be carried out on the scaled system. The payload fractions obtained in the two cases are approximately 0.33 and 0.43, values greater than in the NEP case of the mission to Mars; this too is an expected result, in line with the advantages provided by bimodal systems which, generally, allow, thanks to the improved efficiency in the use of the propellant, to increase the transportable payload mass [13,14].

Table 5: Hybrid Mission Analysis Outputs

Parameter	Value
First Segment	
Mass propellant ratio	0.4
Δv (km/s)	6.7
Time (days)	211
Second Segment	
Mass propellant ratio	0.4
Δv (km/s)	7.88
Time (days)	184
Entire Mission	
Δv (km/s)	14.58
Time (days)	395

These preliminary mission analyses, in which scenarios and parameters were arbitrarily selected, have allowed for determining some constraints for the BANTER system. These constraints will characterize the initial design of the various subsystems and be updated if changes to the mission scenario are necessary due to modifications in the layout of the system's components. The previous analyses, although they have yielded promising results in terms of transit times, initial mass in NSO (considering that some current launchers and even future launcher classes will have the capacity to orbit systems with masses ranging from 30 to 50 t [15–17]), and payload fraction, did not go into detail about the operation of the individual subsystems; the next steps of the system analysis will be combined with the performance studies that the various subsystems can provide to determine the actual capabilities of BANTER. For example, constraints on the operational time of the electric thrusters have been obtained; these constraints determine the continuous time for which the PGS must produce electrical power. The open, asynchronous Brayton cycle solution causes ammonia vapor to accumulate over time inside the tank, which must be emptied once a certain pressure is reached to allow the turbine's nominal operations. The PGS sizing must therefore provide an estimate of the time the system can operate before the tank is emptied and, consequently, an estimate of the quantity of ammonia required to meet the time constraint imposed by the mission analysis. In the case the result demonstrates that the amount of ammonia to be loaded at the start of the mission does not satisfy the constraint on the total initial mass (i.e., the constraint of inserting the system into orbit with a single launch), then, an iterative procedure must be established to modify the PGS design and repeat the mission analysis, taking into account the current performance of the PGS but keeping the key requirements unchanged.

7. Methodology for Preliminary Subsystems Sizing

7.1 Nuclear Reactor

If from the neutronic point of view, it is necessary that, once the materials have been selected, the reactor has appropriate dimensions to reach criticality, it is not certain that these dimensions are sufficient to obtain the thrust required by the mission; in these cases (almost all cases), the dimensions of the reactor are dominated by the thermo-hydraulics. The neutrons circulating in the reactor release energy in the form of heat by hitting the nuclei of the materials composing the various elements of the reactor; this heat is absorbed by the flow of propellant that passes through special channels created in the structure of the reactor, the thrust generated by the system is proportional to the mass flow of the propellant in the reactor and to the temperature it reaches, and, therefore, also to the power of the reactor; it is easy to understand that the greater the thrust required for the same propellant used, the greater the mass flow to be heated in the reactor and the larger the dimensions of the reactor. The sizing of a nuclear

propulsion system is driven by neutronic and thermo-hydraulic/propulsion aspects for which it is necessary to carry out coupled iterative analyses. Neutron analyses (usually conducted with Monte Carlo simulation codes [18,19]), allow to determine the k_{eff} achieved by a given nuclear reactor configuration given as input and allow to obtain as output the power density profile generated by the reactor. This profile can be inserted into a thermo-hydraulic analysis code (be it lumped parameters or one or more dimensions) to determine the properties of the propellant flow passing through the reactor and the temperatures of the various components. However, the properties of the reactor's components are an input for the neutron codes since the estimate of the k_{eff} of the nuclear reactor depends on them: the two analyses are therefore coupled since the outputs of one represent the boundary conditions for the other. Ultimately, to effectively size a nuclear reactor for NTP, it is essential to use an iterative procedure that leads to convergence of the results obtained from the neutron analysis and the thermo-hydraulic analysis; this process is reported in Fig. 3, where use was made of the calorically perfect gas hypothesis for the thrust formulation, an assumption generally accepted to simplify the multi-physical analysis [20].

Fig. 3: Multiphysical Approach for Nuclear Reactor Sizing

7.2 Electric Pumps

Preliminary sizing of the pumps, necessary for determining the power required for their operation, which will influence the PGS and the nuclear reactor design, can be performed using the methodology described in [21]. The first parameters needed for this sizing are: the propellant (liquid propellant density ρ_p), the inlet pressure (p_{in}), the outlet pressure (p_{out}), the pressure inside the reactor (p_c), the propellant mass flow (\dot{m} , depending on the selected thrust level and the nuclear reactor outlet temperature), and the pump type, from which the specific speed (n_s). The power required by the pump (W) is estimated using Eq.(1):

$$P_{pump} = \frac{p_{out} - p_{in}}{\rho_p} \dot{m} . \quad (1)$$

At this point, the pump's mass can be estimated, following [21], as:

$$m_{pump} = \frac{\left[1 + \frac{p_{out} - p_{in}}{p_c} - \frac{p_{in}}{p_c} \right] p_c \dot{m} t_b}{\rho_p P_{pump}} \quad (2)$$

where t_b is the longest engine burn. Since the BANTER system uses E-pumps, it is also necessary to size the motor and the inverter, which are essential components for correct operation. Following again [21], the mass of the electric motor (m_e) can be determined starting from the power required by it using the power density indicated by the supplier (δ_e) or a specific model. The model is selected starting from the number of revolutions required by the pump:

$$N_p = \frac{n_s \left(\frac{P_{out} - P_{in}}{\rho_p} \right)^{\frac{3}{4}}}{\left(\frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_p} \right)^{0.5}}, \quad (3)$$

$$N_p(\text{input}) \rightarrow \text{electric motor model} \rightarrow \eta_e, \delta_e (\text{outputs}), \quad (4)$$

$$P_e = \frac{P_{pump}}{\eta_e}, \quad (5)$$

$$m_e = \frac{P_e}{\delta_e}. \quad (6)$$

In the same way, the inverter mass can be determined starting from the efficiency (η_i) and the power density (δ_i) of the selected model:

$$P_i = \frac{P_e}{\eta_i}, \quad (7)$$

$$m_i = \frac{P_i}{\delta_i}. \quad (8)$$

These rules apply to all E-pumps in the BANTER system and can provide a preliminary estimate of the required masses and powers; these will serve as input for the sizing of the electric power generation system.

7.3 Batteries

A crucial aspect of the BANTER system concerns the PGS's dependence on the nuclear reactor. The thermodynamic cycle can only function when the reactor operates under steady-state conditions with ammonia flowing through it; this means that during the reactor start-up phase, the thermodynamic cycle cannot generate electrical power, and, therefore, the PGS must rely on other components to generate the power needed for the pumps to start the flow of propellant and working fluid (ammonia) within the reactor. Using rechargeable batteries will allow their capacity to be restored during nominal PGS operation, exploiting any surplus power generated. In particular, to size rechargeable batteries, it is necessary to identify the discharge and recharge phases and determine how much energy is stored during the second phase and how much is discharged during the first phase. Table 6 shows these phases.

Table 6: BANTER Batteries Phases

Engine Operation	Batteries Phase
Nuclear Reactor Nominal Operations	Charging Phase
Nuclear Reactor Start-up	Discharging Phase
Nuclear Reactor Shutdown	Discharging Phase

Among the two discharging phases, the start-up phase is generally the most energy-intensive. Batteries must therefore be sized to provide the maximum energy required during this phase. Once the maximum energy required by the batteries has been determined, the energy density of the selected model allows for estimating their mass [21,22]. The flow rate that must pass through the nuclear reactor before reaching steady-state operating conditions determines the energy required by the pumps during the start-up phase; this can be done using a simplified multiphysics analysis. The analysis must address the nuclear reactor transient from both a neutron and a thermo-hydraulic perspective. To do this, the point kinetic equation [23] and the balance equations for unsteady flow must be applied to the entire reactor and the coolant channels, respectively. Recalling the reactor configuration used as the initial layout, i.e., an axially crossed particle bed with four rings of coolant channels, the following strategy can be implemented.

The strategy adopted assumes a lumped parameter approach (quantities independent on the space variable), but it considers the four type of coolant channels separately by inserting in the model the governing equations for each of them. In total, there are 1 equation for the reactor power kinetic, 6 equations for the delayed neutrons precursor groups, 12 equations for the 4 channels fuel and propellant properties (3 eqs. per channel).

During the start-up phase the power level of the nuclear reactor can be estimated using the modified point kinetic equation:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{(\xi(t, T_f, T_p) - \beta_{eff})}{\Lambda_{eff}} P(t) + \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i'(t), \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{dC_i'}{dt} = \frac{\beta_{i,eff}}{\Lambda_{eff}} P(t) - \lambda_i C_i'(t), \quad (10)$$

where P is the reactor power (W), C_i' is the modified concentration of i -th delayed neutron precursor group ($=C_i/\alpha_F$ with α_F conversion factor from neutron flux to reactor power) and the beta and lambda parameters are defined according to the value reported in Table 7 for a space PBR configuration [24].

Table 7: PKE Parameters

Gro up	1	2	3	4	5	6
λ_i (s^{-1})	0.0	0.03	0.11	0.30	1.14	3.01
	12	05	1	1		
	4					
$\beta_{i,eff}$	0.0	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	00	165	147	314	099	002
	31					
Λ_{eff} (s)				3.92e-5		
β_{eff}				0.00758		

The reactivity change ξ is expressed as:

$$\xi = \frac{k_{eff} - 1}{k_{eff}} + \xi_0 \quad (11)$$

where ξ_0 ($= \frac{k_{eff0} - 1}{k_{eff0}}$) is the initial reactivity and k_{eff} is determined using the polynomial laws as function of control drum angles (function of time by the imposed rotating speed), fuel temperature and propellant temperature.

The temperature of the TRISO particle at the different time steps can be determined by integrating the following equation:

$$m_{part} c_{p,part} \frac{dT_f}{dt} = q''(t) - U(T_f - T_p), \quad (12)$$

where the various quantities can be estimated using the approach of [2]:

$$m_{part} = \sum_{i=1}^4 m_i, \quad (13)$$

$$m_i = \frac{r_i^3 - r_{i+1}^3}{3r_1^2} \rho_i, \quad (14)$$

with the i -th layer mass' unit in kg/m^2

$$c_{p,part} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^4 m_i c_{p_i}}{m_{part}}, \quad (15)$$

$$U = \frac{U_t h}{f_p h + U_t}, \quad (16)$$

$$f_p = \frac{1}{2m_{part} c_{p,part}} [m_1 c_{p1} f_1 + m_2 c_{p2} (f_1 + f_2) + m_3 c_{p3} (f_2 + f_3) + m_4 c_{p4} (f_3 - 1)], \quad (17)$$

$$U_t = \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 \frac{1}{U_i} \right)^{-1}, \quad (18)$$

$$U_i = \left(\frac{r_i r_{i+1}}{r_i - r_{i+1}} \right) \frac{k_i}{r_i^2}, \quad (19)$$

$$U_4 = \frac{2k_4}{3r_1}, \quad (20)$$

$$f_1 = \frac{U_t}{U_1}; \quad f_2 = \frac{U_t}{U_2} + f_1; \quad f_3 = \frac{U_t}{U_3} + f_2, \quad (21)$$

$$h = \rho_p u_p c_{p_p} C_h. \quad (22)$$

$q''(t)$ is, for each of the four types of channel, determined by using the power that channel at the nominal power (100 MW), scaling it using the ratio between the power at the considered time step and the nominal power ($\frac{P(t)}{P_{nom}}$) and dividing the result for the factor representing the particle surface area (A_v):

$$A_v = \frac{6V_{channel}(1-\varepsilon)^2}{D_p}. \quad (23)$$

The propellant temperature in the four channels is given by the integration of the energy equation:

$$\rho_p V_p c_{v_p} \frac{dT_p}{dt} = Q_{in} + 2\dot{m} c_{p_p} (T_{in} - T_p), \quad (24)$$

$$Q_{in} = A_v U (T_f - T_p). \quad (25)$$

While, once fixed the pressure drop across the bed, as suggested in [25], the propellant mass flow rate can be estimated from the following equation:

$$\frac{d\dot{m}}{dt} = \frac{A_{channel}}{L_{channel}} \left[(p_{in} - p_{out}) - \frac{R_{cv} \dot{m}^2}{\rho_p} \right] \quad (26)$$

where the resistance term ($\frac{R_{cv} \dot{m}^2}{\rho_p}$) is calculated using the Ergun approach.

The described approach allows for determining the mass flow profile at the reactor inlet to achieve a specific pressure drop during the startup phase. The mass flow profile enables the estimation of the power consumed by the pumps during startup and, therefore, the energy required by the PGS batteries; this will be added to the energy needed to start the PGS electric pumps, which will begin operating once the reactor has reached nominal power and will allow for starting the power generation via the thermodynamic cycle.

The proposed sizing strategies will be the first to be implemented in the BANTER system analysis, as they are fundamental to the preliminary design of the reactor and PGS, which constitute the heart of the entire system. Without them, neither the NTP nor the NEP would be possible. These sizing strategies will provide the performance, dimensions, and masses of the reactor and PGS components, revealing whether the system will be able to meet the constraints imposed by the mission analyses.

8. BANTER Safety Aspects

Safety is a main theme when analyzing a mission involving the use of NTP. As reported in Table 1, among the imposed key requirements a great portion is constituted by safety requirements. The following section shows the rationales adopted for the formulation of such requirements.

Concerning the safety of operations of a nuclear propulsion system in orbit and following the in Sec. 1 described UN COPUOS principles and the Safety Framework for the use of nuclear power sources in outer space, first, a shield must be designed to protect the payload from radiation coming from the reactor. In the preliminary layout, a shadow shield configuration was assumed for the protection of the payload from radiation with maximum permissible dose values taken from [26]; these values refer to the maximum equivalent dose considered bearable by a payload in accordance with the results of the SNAP-10A mission and are therefore not suitable for the protection of astronauts in a crewed mission. The shadow shield strategy makes it possible to considerably reduce the mass and envelope of the nuclear reactor shield. However, it allows for protection from radiation coming from the reactor only in a precise region of the surrounding space, i.e. the one adjacent to the payload fairing. In a mission involving the docking of a nuclear-powered kick-stage on a space station, such as the Lunar Gateway, it is necessary to carefully analyze the docking site to prevent unshielded reactor's radiation from reaching an inadequately protected space station's module. According to [27], during the docking of nuclear propulsion systems, a cold reactor gives a considerably reduced radiological hazard during the docking phase. However, it is worth considering a hot reactor during these operations in order to impose safety conditions suitable for the worst-case scenario. In any case, [27] suggests that it is essential that the docking area on the station is on the opposite side of the nuclear reactor and that there is sufficient distance between the docking ports and the shadow shield. In the case of BANTER, the docking ports should be located at the end of the spacecraft where the payload resides, in the area furthest from the reactor, and included within the protection cone generated by the shadow shield. In this way, during the payload loading and unloading operations between the space-tug on which BANTER will be inserted and the docked space station, the maximum dose that reaches the docked module would be lower than the imposed limits and considered not dangerous for uncrewed missions.

Another safety concern regarding using nuclear propulsion systems is the EOL disposal orbit. Generally, these propulsion systems are planned to be placed in a sufficiently high lifetime orbit so that all their radioactive inventory has decayed before their possible re-entry into the Earth's atmosphere [27]. As also described for the MAPS project, which involved a mission in the cislunar environment, as one of the scenarios analyzed in this work, at the end of the mission, with the last propellant load obtained in lunar orbit, the system has a Δv of about 4.1 km/s available with which it can position itself in an ultra-long life orbit starting from an orbit around the Lagrangian point L2 thus posing a virtually zero risk of radioactive material re-entering the Earth's atmosphere. A similar precaution shall be adopted for the operations at BOL: the nuclear propulsion system can start its mission only when it reaches a Nuclear Safe Orbit (NSO) defined as a sufficiently high orbital altitude where a nuclear-powered spacecraft can be placed such that the orbital lifetime is long enough for the radioactive inventory of the core to decay below acceptable levels before any potential re-entry in the case of premature mission abortion [28,29].

Another main aspect to consider, in addition to safety during nominal operation and final disposal, is the safety of an accidental atmospheric reentry of the propulsion system. Reentry is a serious problem for this type of system, as demonstrated by the RORSAT missions accomplished by the USSR [30]. In these missions using nuclear reactors for power generation, a redundant safety system should have prevented the nuclear reactor from reentering the Earth's atmosphere. The first system was a reactor ejection system, which should have displaced the nuclear reactor in a high-safe orbit. In the event of failure of this primary system, the second system should have to eject the reactor and disperse the radioactive components to minimize the risk of radioactive pollution of the Earth's atmosphere. However, in at least four cases these safety systems failed (due to unreliability problems that were quite common in Soviet satellites of the time), and the nuclear reactor reentered the atmosphere causing international accidents. Fortunately, only in one case the radioactive material scattered on the ground in an area of about 124000 km² [30].

According to [31], there are several different scenarios in which a nuclear fission reactor reentry can occur; the reactor's fuel can be hot or cold, the reactor can be critical or subcritical, and during the reentry, the core can completely burn up, or land intact or break apart and land scattered. The total dose to the public is the main concern regarding the atmospheric reentry of a nuclear system. In the case of a cold reactor reentry neither direct radiation nor dispersal from impact causes any significant dose, and according to [31], this kind of reentry is not an issue unless the reactor becomes critical after the impact. In the case of hot reactor reentry, the public can receive a dose from the release of fission products and direct gamma radiation. Obviously, the reentry of a nuclear reactor into the atmosphere is an accidental event, and there is no control over whether the reactor will be cold or hot. Therefore, considering the worst case in which the reactor is hot, as previously written, it can reenter in three ways: intact, burn completely in the atmosphere, or reenter scattered. The scattered reentry is an event to avoid, as the lesson of the RORSAT missions has taught as it significantly increases the impact area of radioactive material involving a possible greater number of people by releasing high doses in multiple sites and making recovery operations more complicated. For this reason, it is better to design the propulsion system in such a way as to ensure the integrity of the reactor or its complete burning at high altitudes in the event of an accidental reentry into the Earth's atmosphere. In both cases, additional systems and masses add to the system; the intact reentry requires reactor protection systems such as aeroshells, while the disintegration of the reactor requires active systems and mechanisms for the burning of the various components since the materials composing the reactor resist high temperatures and it is not certain that aerothermal loading alone is capable of completely burning and vaporizing the entire reactor. Trade-offs are necessary to determine which of the two solutions provides the best compromise between system mass and reliability. For example, using a PBR it could be easier to break up the reactor during reentry since the nuclear fuel is in the form of small separate particles very easily divisible and not a single monolithic block as in prismatic reactors; however, a malfunction of the active reactor disintegration system could lead to a scattered reentry and to a worst-case scenario. Therefore, it could be preferable to have a controlled intact reentry, which however requires large additional mass to the system and complicated reactor recovery operations. In addition, in the case of accidental reentry of the reactor, as [27] underlines, from the point of view of nonproliferation and safety, a scenario with LEU reactors rather than HEU is much better; cores using ^{235}U with an enrichment lower than 20% wt. make the safety of intact or scattered impact reactor recovery operations much less of an issue.

To date, there are no precise international agreements regarding the risks of inadvertent reentry of nuclear reactors, which provide a guide to follow during the design of a nuclear propulsion system. However, the work done by Camp et al. [31] can be used as a preliminary guideline to address this issue in the early stages of design. The main points are:

- the likelihood of an inadvertent reentry be $< 10^{-4}$ over the mission life;
- the combined probability of inadvertent reentry plus scattering to be $< 10^{-6}$;
- in the case of space tug missions, the events may occur multiple times during a mission lifetime and the probabilities must be added together;
- in the case of intact reentry, the scattering of radioactive components should be confined to an impact zone with a radius of less than 1 km.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that Proust et al. [32] faced the problem of an inadvertent reentry of the propulsion system during the MAPS project. Their solution was to raise the system's operational orbit around the Earth to an altitude such as to have a sufficiently long lifetime to eliminate the problem of a radiologically hot reentry of the propulsion system based on the expected radiological inventory that the system would have accumulated during its operational life. This solution can be explored once the mission profile (operating hours of the reactor), the type of reactor, and the design of the space tug (as the drag coefficient influences the decay from the operational orbit) have been precisely established, since, as indicated in [29], the orbit can range from 400 km to 1300 km, based on these reported factors. One last issue pointed out during the MAPS project is the launch abort. In this case, the reactor has no radioactive products since it is at the beginning of its life, and thanks to the control drums, it should be subcritical: the only problem could emerge following core reconfigurations caused by a system impact after a failed launch. To reduce the likelihood of criticality achieved after a reconfiguration, the authors of the MAPS project suggested

making the moderator/reflector in one single block. All these precautions to ensure the safety of the operations of the proposed system will have to be immediately in the early stages of system design.

All the safety aspects of nuclear propulsion systems just reported influenced the determination of BANTER's key safety requirements. It is worth noticing that these requirements were arbitrarily imposed by the consortium and do not derive from any European or Global legislation imposed on these types of systems, which is currently absent.

9. Conclusions

BANTER is an innovative bimodal propulsion system consisting of several closely interconnected systems (nuclear thermal propulsion system, nuclear electric propulsion system, power generation system, propellant management system, and attitude control system), all powered by a single substance: ammonia. The strong connection between the various subsystems makes BANTER's development non-trivial, starting with the formulation of requirements and the identification of design-driving factors. For this reason, the first six months of the four-year project were dedicated to system engineering and mission analysis for identifying the best strategies for the subsequent design and development phases. Starting from some essential requirements on which the BANTER project is based, a mission analysis divided into three main strands demonstrated the advantages of using the bimodal system and the main constraints to be applied to the system during the preliminary design phases. These phases will begin with the sizing of the most critical elements, namely the nuclear reactor and the electric power generation system. The nuclear reactor is the central component of BANTER, and its correct sizing determines the feasibility of the proposed system layout and the performance of every other element. The power generation system enables the use of both the NEP and the NTP, and together with the reactor, determines the level of performance achievable by these subsystems. Consequently, its design allows for verifying the input hypotheses for the mission analyses conducted. This work shows the methodology that will be followed in sizing the various components of the PGS in parallel with the design of the nuclear reactor. Iterations with the mission analyses may be necessary to achieve a configuration that satisfies the established key requirements. Among the key requirements, safety requirements are particularly notable. In the absence of globally recognized standards for the safety of using nuclear systems in orbit, a literature review has highlighted the main aspects and issues related to safety, from which crucial requirements have been derived concerning, among others, the re-entry, injection into orbit, and final disposal of BANTER. All these topics and preliminary results are just the first step in BANTER's system analysis. In the coming months, the project will address designing the main subsystems and innovative technologies to be demonstrated. Different research groups will address these tasks, and the system engineering's role will be to coordinate the efforts and verify that the layouts proposed for the various subsystems can be integrated with each other while meeting the imposed requirements and the design-driving factors. The goal will be to converge the several technologies developed within the BANTER project into a single system with a TRL of 4.

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